

Spiders from irrigated ricefields. Valle del Cauca Department, Colombia, 1990-91.

Taxon	Locality
Anyphaenidae	
<i>Anyphaena</i> (near) <i>affinis</i>	Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Araneidae	
<i>Alpaida trispinosa</i> (Keyserling)	Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Alpaida veniliae</i> (Keyserling)	Paso de la Torre
<i>Argiope argentata</i> (F.)	Caloto, Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Argiope trifasciata</i> (Forsk.)	Palmira, Ginebra, Paso de la Torre
<i>Cyclosa walckenaeri</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge)	Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Eriophora</i> sp.	Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Eustala fuscovittata</i> (Keyserling)	Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Gasteracantha cancriformis</i> (L.)	Caloto, Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Gea heptagon</i> (Hentz)	Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson)	Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Clubionidae	
<i>Cheiracanthium inclusum</i> (Hentz)	Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Linyphiidae	
<i>Centromerus</i> sp.	Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Lycosidae	
<i>Pardosa near saxatilis</i> (Hentz)	Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Pardosa milvina</i> (Hentz)	Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Oxyopidae	
<i>Oxyopes salticus</i> (Hentz)	Caloto, Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Tetragnathidae	
<i>Tetragnatha straminea</i> Emerton	Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Tetragnatha</i> sp.	Palmira, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Metidae	
<i>Leucauge argyra</i> (Walkenaer)	Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Leucauge</i> sp.	Jamundí
Theridiidae	
<i>Chryso pulcherrima</i> (Mello-Leitao)	Palmira, Paso de la Torre
<i>Theridula gonygaster</i> Simon	Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Thomisidae	
<i>Misumenops pallida</i> Keyserling	Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Misumenoides paucispinosus</i> Keyserling	Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
<i>Synaemops rubropunctatum</i> Mello-Leitao	Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre
Salticidae	
<i>Paraphidippus</i> sp.	Palmira, Jamundí
<i>Phidippus clarus</i> Keyserling	Palmira, Ginebra, Jamundí, Paso de la Torre

until harvest. Experts in Brazil, USA, and the Philippines identified them.

Twenty-seven species belonging to 23 genera and 11 families were identified (see table). The most abundant families in descending order were Tetragnathidae,

Salticidae, and Lycosidae. Araneidae was the family with the most species (10) from eight genera. Studies are underway to determine the importance of these species in controlling rice pests. ■

IRRN REMINDER

Multiple submissions. Normally, only one report for a single experiment will be accepted. Two or more items about the same work submitted at the same time will be returned for merging. Submitting at different times multiple notes from the same experiment is highly inappropriate. Detection will result in the rejection of all submissions on that research.

Integrated pest management—other pests

Ground golden snail *Ampullarius (Pomacea) canaliculata* as fertilizer increases rice yield

R. R. Aquino, University of Southern Mindanao, Kabacan, Cotabato, Philippines

Golden snails are abundant in the Philippines, causing much damage to lowland rice plants. Golden snails must be picked and placed on roads or in areas without water to eliminate them from ricefields.

Masses of golden snail were gathered, crushed, and sun-dried for 3-4 d. Crushed snails were then hammer-milled and basally applied as organic fertilizer to direct seeded IR74 at 0, 0.25, 0.5, and 0.75 t/ha during wet (WS) and dry seasons (DS) on a clay loam soil in lower Paatan, Kabacan, Cotabato, Philippines. Results were significant. An increase in yield of about 50% at 0.75 t/ha equivalent application rate over the control was attributed to the ground snail fertilizer, which has 94.78% dry matter, 16.49% crude protein, and 2.54% ether extract.

The procedure eradicates the pest and increases rice yield. ■

Effect of different levels of ground golden snail on yield of irrigated rice.^a

Application rate (t/ha)	Mean yield (t/ha)	
	WS	DS
0.25	3.7 a	4.8 b
0.50	4.9 b	5.0 b
0.75	5.4 c	5.3 c
Control	3.6 a	3.8 a

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Four replications.